

THERMOFORMING SIMULATION OF THERMOPLASTIC PRE-IMPREGNATED TEXTILE REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a shell and membrane hybrid FE model of CFRTP for non-isothermal forming in order to capture the deformation during the process. The proposed model can describe the out-of-plane bending behavior which is independently free from in-plane behavior. Temperature dependent anisotropic in-plane behavior is represented by calculating the stress contributions of the textile reinforcement and the thermoplastic separately. Reuss model which can take the volume fraction of fiber into account is applied to the stress calculation of in-plane thermoplastic to accurately predict the shear behavior which is the key deformation mode during forming. The temperature dependent out-of-plane and in-plane material characteristics are grasped by the 3-point-bending and bias-extension experiments conducted in the range of the process temperature. The FE model is constructed based on the experimental results. Non-isothermal forming simulations for S-rail shape and automotive backdoor panel are presented, and the results are compared to experimental results. The simulated outline and shear angle are in good agreement with the experimental results. The sensitivity study shows that the effect of the temperature plays an important role in deformation during a non-isothermal forming process.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing requirement for crash safety with weight reduction in the automotive industry has gradually expanded the use of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP). One of the reasons for the expansion is that the development of resin transfer molding (RTM) has reduced its cycle time to less than 10 minutes. However, further shortening is required in order to be applied to the mass production

of cars since the production cycle time needs to be less than 1 minute. Therefore thermoforming process of a carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) has increased its presence in the industry since it is a faster manufacturing process than RTM process which needs a long curing stage.

Finite element analysis (FEA) as an alternative approach for experimental study is effective in designing fiber reinforced plastic products because there are many design parameters such as fiber type, resin type, morphology of fiber, volume fraction of fiber (V_f), fiber orientation, etc. Forming simulation is especially important because the performance of the final composite part strongly depends on changes in fiber orientation during the forming process. The simulation models in many of existing researches [1-3] ignore bending stiffness as it is significantly low compared to tensile stiffness. Notwithstanding bending stiffness plays a important role in the prediction of wrinkles. In our previous work, a textile reinforcement model for FEA which can consider out-of-plane bending stiffness as well as in-plane anisotropic properties was proposed in order to predict the wrinkling [4]. Thermoforming simulation for thermoplastic pre-pregs is more complex than the simulation for dry textile reinforcement because the material shows temperature and rate dependent behavior as well as anisotropic and nonlinear behavior. Wang et al, [5] and Haanappel et al, [6] proposed temperature and strain rate dependent friction models which can predict accurate slippage behaviour. Chen et al, [7] also proposed a model for a textile thermoplastic pre-preg forming simulation which considers the influence of the strain rate by adding a viscosity to the anisotropic hyperelastic model. These models [6-8] focused on isothermal forming simulation thus they did not consider the change in the temperature and material properties during forming. A non-isothermal forming for CFRTP can shorten its cycle time to less than isothermal forming since it requires no heating and cooling times. Non-isothermal forming has a limited design window because of the rapidly cooling pre-consolidated laminate and the decreasing formability which is caused by contact with the tool. So the temperature condition during forming should be carefully designed. Thus it is very important to simulate temperature change within the laminates and change in material properties due to temperature change.

The primary focus of this paper is on FE modeling and simulations performed to capture the forming behavior of a textile thermoplastic pre-preg. The possibility of extending the textile reinforcement model in the previous study [4] to the thermoplastic pre-preg model for non-isothermal forming simulation is investigated. A model of thermoplastic pre-preg which can consider the temperature dependent in-plane and out-of-plane properties is constructed based on the results of bias-extension and three-point bending experiments which are conducted in the range of the process temperatures. Non-isothermal forming simulations for S-rail shape and automotive backdoor panel are performed and compared to experimental results. Simulated outline and shear angle are in good agreement with experimental results. Moreover, sensitivity study suggests that the effect of the temperature plays a dominant role in deformation during thermoforming processes.

2 MODELLING STRATEGY FOR THERMOPLASTIC PRE-PREG

In our previous study [4], we proposed the shell and membrane hybrid model in order to consider the bending stiffness that is independently free from any in-plane properties. In-plane properties are described by the membrane element and the bending stiffness is represented by a set of elements which consist of two shell elements with the membrane element in between. Figure 1 shows the composition of our proposed model.

Figure 1: Shell and membrane hybrid model for dry textile reinforcement.

The normal direction of the shell element is defined as z , and $z=0$ on the mid-surface. The strains of two shell elements from the rotational displacement of the node are calculated as being placed at an equal distance opposite from the node position of the membrane elements. The distance from the mid-surface of the shell elements is d , the thicknesses to be given to the shell elements are $t/2$ respectively. The strain of the offset shells against the rotational deformation is greatly calculated according to the offset distance, d . This means the offset of the shell reference surface is applied to increase the effect of bending moment, M_y . As a result, we can give a small Young's modulus to the two shell elements. It is enough to get effective bending stiffness, but not enough to affect the in-plane properties. It is assumed that there is no interaction between the bending stiffness and in-plane deformation.

The objective is to extend the textile reinforcement model to the thermoplastic pre-preg model. In order to add the effect of thermoplastic resin to the textile reinforcement model, additional membrane elements are placed around the textile membrane. In-plane stress response of the pre-preg is represented in a parallel system of textile reinforcement and thermoplastic resin where those stresses are separately calculated. Figure 2 shows the schematic of the thermoplastic pre-preg model for non-isothermal forming simulation.

Figure 2: Modeling schematic of textile thermoplastic pre-preg.

The thermoplastic material is elasto-plastic material which considers thermal effects. The stress contribution of the thermoplastic in yarn direction, 0/90, is much less important than in 45/45 direction since the stiffness of the yarn is much higher than the stiffness of the thermoplastic. Therefore the main purpose of the additive stress contribution of the thermoplastic on the textile is to describe the in-plane shear response of the pre-preg.

Figure 3: Schematic illustration of textile as superposed two UD layers.

To simplify the meso-scale material structure, the textile pre-preg is made up of two different superposed layers which consist of unidirectional fibers (UD layer) as shown in Figure 3. The fiber direction of first layer is oriented initially at 90° with respect to the second layer. Each layer is deformed freely without any interaction. As a result of this simplified assumption, any effect of textile

architecture becomes ignorable. Reuss model [8], which was developed from the assumption of equal stress in fiber and resin and is often used to predict the in-plane shear property of a UD material as an elementary micromechanical approach, can be adapted to the stress calculation of resin in each layer under in-plane shear deformation. The stress of the thermoplastic is calculated by:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^m = \frac{\varepsilon_{ij} - V_f \varepsilon_{ij}^f}{(1 - V_f)} \quad (1)$$

Where ε_{ij}^m is a thermoplastic strain which is calculated based on Reuss model. ε_{ij} and ε_{ij}^f are the macro strain of the pre-preg and the fiber strain respectively. V_f is the fiber volume fraction. Here, $\varepsilon_{ij} \gg \varepsilon_{ij}^f$ because the fiber stiffness is usually much higher than resin stiffness, ε_{ij}^m can be approximated as:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^m = \frac{\varepsilon_{ij}}{(1 - V_f)} \quad (2)$$

Elements for the textile model and the thermoplastic model undergo the same displacement as they are represented in a parallel system. However the strain of the thermoplastic is calculated by introducing eq. (2).

3 CONSTRUCTION OF THERMOPLASTIC PRE-PREG MODEL

The textile thermoplastic pre-preg tested in this work is composed of plain weave carbon fiber fabric and polymethyl-methacrylate (PMMA) resin. PMMA is a thermoplastic polymer. The temperature of glass-liquid transition (T_g) of PMMA is 108°C. Pre-consolidated laminate that has four pre-preg layers is produced by a hot press at a temperature above the melting point of PMMA. V_f of the laminate after pre-consolidation is 70% and the thickness of the laminate with 4 ply is 0.84mm on average.

3.1 In-plane model, bias-extension test

A large in-plane shear deformation typically occurs during the forming of a textile laminate since the in-plane shear resistance is very low until the textile laminate reaches the shear locking angle. Thus accurately expressing the in-plane shear behavior of a textile laminate is very important for accurate forming simulation as mentioned before. A bias-extension test is a popular approach to measure the shear property of a textile laminate. It is a tensile test performed on a rectangular specimen where the warp and weft yarns are oriented initially 45/-45 to the direction of applied tensile load. In this study, bias-extension tests were performed at five different temperatures, 50, 100, 150, 180 and 200°C.

Simulations of the bias-extension tests are also performed at five different temperatures. The stress-strain relationships of PMMA under T_g , 50 and 100°C, used for the simulations are taken from CAMPUS database [9]. Those over T_g , 150, 180 and 200°C are identified by fitting the experimental results since there is no database of stress-strain relationships over T_g . Figure 4 shows comparisons of load responses between experimental measurements and simulations.

From the experimental measurements (black and blue dot lines in Figure 4), the temperature dependent shear property has to be considered, especially for non-isothermal forming because the in-plane shear property strongly depends on temperature during the forming. The experimental results at 180 and 200°C were similar to each other. At temperatures higher than T_g , we observed the peeling of the interlayer and squeeze flow of thermoplastic resin after the shear locking. At the same time, the jagged edge found after the bias-extension test revealed that the test had induced intra-ply slip between yarns as well as trellising after shear locking. Thus we understand the bias-extension test results appear to be valid before it reaches the shear locking angle.

The simulations of the bias-extension tests have been done by LS-DYNA [10] with the proposed thermoplastic pre-preg model. The simulation responses are shown in Figure 4 (red solid lines), along with the experimental measurements. Regarding the temperature range under T_g , Figure 4 (a) and (b), red lines show the results of simulation applying Reuss model. On the other hand, blue lines show the results of simulation using original stress-strain relationship of PMMA not applying Reuss model. We

can see the shear response applying Reuss model is more similar to that of experiments than the result not applying Reuss model. Regarding the temperature range over T_g , a good correlation with the experimental force up to shear locking angle over T_g is obtained by adjusting the properties of PMMA.

Figure 4: Comparisons of in-plane shear responses under bias-extension tests.

3.2 Out-of-plane model, 3-point bending test

Next, we conducted 3-point bending tests at three different temperatures, 50, 75 and 100°C in order to understand the temperature dependent bending property. The simulations of 3-point bending tests were also conducted in order to describe the temperature dependent out-of-plane bending behavior. Figure 5 shows the comparison between the experimental results and simulated results. We can see good agreements up to a maximum flexural stress at every temperature.

Figure 5: Comparison of out-of-plane bending responses under 3-point bending tests.

4 THERMOFORMING SIMULATIONS

4.1 S-rail thermoforming simulations and sensitivity study

Pre-consolidated laminates consist of four textile thermoplastic pre-preg layers. Simple laminates with $[(0/90)]_4$ and $[(45/-45)]_4$ lay-ups were tested experimentally in order to assess the capability of the proposed FE model. The blank was cut in square form, 250mm×250mm. S-rail forming experiments were performed with a non-heated metal tool at room temperature. First, the pre-consolidated laminate was heated to forming temperature separately in an oven. Then it was rapidly transferred to a forming tool and formed by the downward movement of the punch at a speed of 20mm/s. The temperature of the laminate, which was measured just before the forming process, was uniformly distributed over the majority of the surface area. Its average temperature was 185°C which were measured by thermography. Temperature within the laminate of the $[(0/90)]_4$ during the non-isothermal forming was monitored by using thermocouples. All thermocouples were embedded at the center of thickness.

Simulations are also performed by two different approaches to investigate the effect of the change in the temperature during the forming. One is non-isothermal simulation by thermal-mechanical coupling analysis which can consider the change in the temperature during forming. The other is isothermal simulation by simple mechanical analysis under the assumption of a constant temperature during the forming process. In non-isothermal forming simulation, the heat transfer conductance between pre-preg laminate and tool is determined by reference to the database of the commercial plastics injection molding software Mox3D [11]. Thermal conductivity of the pre-preg laminate is calculated by Eshelby-based semi-analytical mean-field homogenization approaches in Digimat-MF [12]. Table 1 shows the thermal parameters which are used in this work.

Heat transfer conductance	h	[mJ/(mm ² -s-K)]	3.0
In-plane thermal conductivity of pre-preg	K_{11}, K_{22}	[mJ/(mm-s-K)]	3.4
Out-of-plane thermal conductivity of pre-preg	K_{33}	[mJ/(mm-s-K)]	0.68
Heat capacity of pre-preg	HC	[(mJ)/(g-K)]	1,100

Table 1: Thermal parameters for thermal analysis.

The initial temperature for the blank and steel tools is set at 185°C and 25°C. The die and punch are modeled as rigid bodies. A laminate of four layers is modeled as a single layer by the proposed model as shown in Figure 6. Slippage between the neighboring layers is not taken into account in this study because there was no slippage observed in the experiments.

Figure 6: S-rail thermoforming simulation model of pre-consolidated laminate.

Figure 7 shows the comparisons of the outlines between the experiments and each simulation. The outlines simulated by the non-isothermal simulations show good agreement with the experimental measurements for both laminates with $[(0/90)]_4$ and $[(45/-45)]_4$ lay-ups. On the other hand, the outlines

simulated by the isothermal simulations are different from the experimental measurements for both lay-ups.

Figure 7: Comparison of final outlines between experiments and simulations.

Figure 8: Comparison of temperatures within laminate of [(0/90)₄] lay-up during the forming.

Figure 8 shows the comparisons of temperature-stroke curves between the experiment and the simulation, along with the positions of thermocouples and the temperature distributions in the simulation. The simulated temperature histories during the forming are in good correlation with the experimental measured temperatures. P2 are located in the side wall near the corner of punch. We can observe the temperature of P2 drops during the forming process. This drop is due to contact with the tools from both sides. The shear resistance is dramatically increased by the decreased temperature.

Consequently, the shear deformation in the isothermal simulation is larger than the experiment and the non-isothermal simulation: 71° for the experiment, 61° for the isothermal simulation and 71° for the non-isothermal simulation as shown in Figure 9. This is the reason for the larger draw-in in the isothermal simulation.

These simulation results demonstrated that formability is significantly changing throughout the non-isothermal forming.

Figure 9: Comparison of shear angle between experiment and simulations of $[(0/90)]_4$ layups.

4.2 Forming simulation of automobile backdoor panel

Next, a real automobile part, backdoor panel, was formed experimentally and simulated by the non-isothermal forming simulation.

The blank size for simple laminates with $[(0/90)]_4$ lay-ups is $1400\text{mm} \times 840\text{mm}$. In-plane tensile load in 45 deg. direction is added by restraining the four corners of the blank with pins to reduce the wrinkling during the forming. After the heated blank was rapidly transported towards the tool at room temperature, and formed at a speed of 20mm/s . The final stroke of punch is 82mm . The initial temperatures of blank monitored by thermography showed a uniform distribution and average blank temperatures were 185°C , as in S-rail forming. We obtained the blank sheet is deflected by self-gravity when it is set on the tool.

Figure 10: Isothermal self-gravity simulation before the non-isothermal forming simulation.

Before the non-isothermal forming simulation, the isothermal self-gravity simulation of the heated laminate at 185°C is performed by mechanical analysis as shown in Figure 10. After the self-gravity simulation, the non-isothermal forming simulation are conducted using the thermal parameters at Table 1 again. The initial temperatures of the laminate and tools in the non-isothermal forming simulation are set at 185°C and 25°C respectively. Figure 11 presents the temperature distribution during the forming obtained by non-isothermal simulation. The temperature drops at and around the contact point with the die after self-gravity. Figure 12 shows the comparison of the deformation after forming of backdoor panel of $[(0/90)]_4$ layups. We can observe the large draw-in as shown by the red line in both experiment and simulation. Small wrinkling can be observed in the die face zone in the experiments, however, these cannot be observed in the simulation. Calculations were done by MPP LS-DYNA at 32 cores on Intel Xeon Processor E5-2670. Computing times was 20 hours.

Figure 11: Temperature distribution of laminate during non-isothermal forming.

Figure 12: Comparison of deformation after forming of backdoor panel of $[(0/90)]_4$ layups.

5 CONCLUSION

An FE model for non-isothermal forming simulation of a thermoplastic pre-preg model for the forming of textile reinforcement was proposed in this study. This model has the capability to consider the change in temperature during forming and the temperature dependent material property by thermal-mechanical coupling analysis. For the effect of the temperature dependent material behavior on the forming simulation results, S-rail forming simulations of pre-preg laminate were conducted as well. Results of this sensitivity study pointed out that considering the effect of the temperature is

important to accurately predict deformation during non-isothermal forming. Finally, forming simulation of real automobile part, backdoor panel, was conducted by the proposed model. The deformations predicted agreed well with experimental results.

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